

Synthesis of 4-Aminoquinolines

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4-Anilinoquinolines have been prepared by cyclodehydration of β -anilinoacryloanilides with polyphosphoric acid.

7-Chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy)anilinoquinoline is a key intermediate in the synthesis of the well-known drug, Camoquin. The usual procedure for preparation of 4-aminoquinolines involves condensation of 4-haloquinoline with appropriate amino compounds, both aliphatic and aromatic. The preparation of 4-haloquinolines involves a number of steps. To obviate this, Price and Boekelheide¹, followed by Sen and Basu², have established a general method by which a 4-substituted aminoquinoline could be directly synthesised by cyclodehydration of β -anilinoacrylamides. Thus Sen and Basu² observed that β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide on cyclodehydration with phosphorus oxychloride in benzene provided 7-chloro-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline which on hydrolysis, decarboxylation, and demethylation yielded 7-chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy)anilinoquinoline. On subjecting β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide to cyclodehydration with polyphosphoric acid, 7-chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline has now been obtained in one step in 80% yield. It is therefore significant to note that the ring-closure is taking place with simultaneous hydrolysis of the ethoxycarbonyl group and decarboxylation. Incidentally, similar cyclisation of β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide resulted in cyclodehydration with simultaneous demethylation to afford 7-chloro-4-(4'-hydroxy)anilinoquinoline³. Attempted cyclisation of the compound with concentrated sulphuric acid met with failure. Ethoxycarbonylaceto-*p*-methoxyanilide and β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide were prepared essentially according to Sen and Basu²; the yields were significantly improved by slightly modifying the original procedure.

Similar cyclisation of β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -cyanoacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide led to 7-chloro-3-carboxamido-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline which on hydrolysis and de-

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1246.

2. *This Journal*, 1957, **34**, 906.

3. Sen and Mitra, unpublished.

carboxylation afforded the 7-chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline in a reduced yield. Thermal decarboxylation of the carboxy derivative led to a considerable amount of insoluble carbonaceous material along with the desired decarboxylated product. Treatment with polyphosphoric acid, however, resulted in smooth decarboxylation.

Possibility of a similar cyclisation of β -*m*-chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonyl-*N*-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutyl)acrylamide to afford chloroquine diphosphate directly was then thought to be of considerable interest, which, however, could not be realised. Extrusion of 1-diethylamino-4-aminopentane occurred during cyclodehydration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethoxycarbonylaceto-p-anisidide.—*p*-Anisidine (6.1 g., 0.05 *M*) was added slowly during 60 min. to well-stirred diethyl malonate (32 g., 0.2 *M*), maintained at 170°. The mixture was stirred at 170° for another hour; it was then cooled and the solid collected. Excess of malonic ester was distilled from the mother liquor under reduced pressure. The combined product was then thoroughly washed with petroleum (40-60°), dried, dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol (100 ml), and filtered hot. The dianilide separating on cooling was filtered (yield 1.1 g., m.p. 225-26°). The mother liquor was concentrated to obtain the desired compound (8.5 g., 72%) which on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 69-70°. (The reported² yield is 52% and m.p. 68-70°).

β -*m*-Chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide (Ia) was prepared essentially as described by Sen and Basu². The bath temperature, however, was slowly raised to 120°, kept at that temperature for 1 hr., and finally to 180°, when the distillation of ethanol had ceased. On crystallisation from ethanol the compound (6.5 g., 86%) melted at 113-14°. (The reported² yield is 27.7% and m.p. 114°).

7-Chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline (Ib).— β -*m*-Chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide (6 g.) was slowly added to polyphosphoric acid (prepared by heating a mixture of 9 g. of P₂O₅ and 5.6 ml of 85% H₃PO₄ until the solution was clear), carefully maintaining the temperature below 10°, and the mixture kept overnight. The mixture was then heated on a steam bath for 6 hr. After keeping overnight, it was triturated with ice, the solid was stirred with 1% NaOH solution (100 ml), collected, and washed. On two crystallisations from ethanol the solid (3.6 g., 80%) melted at 211-12°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample² recorded no depression.

*Attempted Cyclodehydration of β -m-Chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide*— β -*m*-Chloroanilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide (1 g.) was slowly added to H₂SO₄ (conc., 1 ml) below 10°. After keeping 30 days at the room temperature, a portion of the mixture was stirred with ice, triturated with ammonia, washed with water, and dried. The original compound was recovered unchanged. The compound, which was isolated after warming the reaction mixture on a steam bath and working up as described above, melted at 278-80° and it was not further investigated.

Cyanoaceto-p-anisidide.—A mixture of *p*-anisidine (9.2 g., 0.075 *M*) and ethyl cyanoacetate (9 g., 0.075 *M*) was slowly heated to 180° and kept at that temperature until theo-

retical amount of ethanol had distilled. The solid residue was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol. The product (10.3 g., 70.5%), obtained on cooling, was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C, 63.35; H, 5.43; N, 14.51. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 14.73%).

*β -m-Chloroanilino- α -cyanoacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide (IIa).*—A mixture of *m*-chloroaniline (5.08 g., 0.04 *M*), ethyl orthoformate (5.92 g., 0.04 *M*), and cyanoaceto-*p*-anisidide (7.6 g., 0.04 *M*) was heated at 120-25° until the required amount of ethanol had distilled. The residual solid on crystallisation from ethanol melted at 142-43°, yield 7.8g., 60%. (Found: C, 62.69; H, 4.46; N, 13.1. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_3Cl$ requires C, 62.29; H, 4.28; N, 12.82%).

7-Chloro-3-carbozamido-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline (IIb).— *β -m-Chloroanilino- α -cyanoacrylo-*p*-methoxyanilide* was cyclised in polyphosphoric acid and worked up to provide the title compound, essentially as described for the ethoxycarbonyl analogue. On crystallisation from ethanol the compound (yield 40%) melted at 189-90°. (Found: C, 62.51; H, 4.52; N, 13.45. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_3Cl$ requires C, 62.29; H, 4.28; N, 12.82%).

7-Chloro-3-carboxy-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline.—The compound (IIb) (1.5 g.) was added to 25% MeOH-KOH solution (25 ml), when it went into solution, but a precipitate began to appear after 1 hr. The mixture was kept overnight. The methanol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in water and acidified to Congo red. The solid was collected, washed with water, and crystallised from aqueous acetic acid, m.p. 280-81°, yield 1.2g., 87% (reported² m.p. 278-80°). (Found: C, 62.41; H, 4.38; N, 8.99. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N_2Cl$: C, 62.10; H, 3.96; N, 8.52%).

7-Chloro-4-(4'-methoxy)anilinoquinoline (Ib).—(a). The carboxy compound (0.9 g., 0.003 *M*) was slowly added to liquid paraffin (4 ml) at 280° $\pm$ 5° and the mixture was kept at that temperature until the gas evolution had ceased. The solid was collected, washed several times with petroleum (40-60°), and extracted with boiling ethanol; the extract was filtered. A considerable amount of carbonaceous material remained undissolved. On concentration, the filtrate deposited the title compound, m.p. 211-12°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample² remained undepressed.

(b). The carboxy compound (0.65 g., 0.002 *M*) was slowly added to polyphosphoric acid (prepared from 0.98 g. of P_2O_5 and 0.58 ml of 85% H_3PO_4) below 10°. The mixture was then heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. and the compound (0.26 g., 50%) isolated as described earlier; m.p. 211-212°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample² recorded no depression.

N-(4-Diethylamino-1-methylbutyl)ethoxycarbonylacetamide.—1-Diethylamino-4-aminopentane (7.9 g., 0.05 *M*) was slowly added to well-stirred diethyl malonate (32 g., 0.2 *M*) at 150° and the mixture kept at the same temperature until the requisite amount of ethanol had distilled. Excess of diethyl malonate was removed and the residual oil was distilled at 178-80°/3 mm, yield 8.4 g., 62%. (Found: C, 61.99; H, 10.66; N, 9.88. $C_{14}H_{26}O_3N_2$ requires C, 61.76; H, 10.29; N, 10.29%).

Attempted Preparation of Chloroquine Diphosphate.—A mixture of *N*-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutyl)ethoxycarbonylacetamide (5.44 g., 0.02 *M*), *m*-chloroaniline (2.54 g., 0.02 *M*), and ethyl orthoformate (2.96 g., 0.02 *M*) was heated slowly at 170-75° until the

distillation of ethanol had ceased. The dark viscous liquid could not be induced to afford any pure material and it was then subjected to cyclisation procedure described earlier. From the reaction mixture no pure product could be isolated. The reaction mixture was then basified with a slight excess of ammonia and extracted with benzene. The oily residue after removal of benzene was then subjected to distillation under reduced pressure. The portion of the material distilled was identified as 1-diethylamino-4-aminopentane.

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